
Analysing the Impact of Corporate Board Attributes on Working Capital Management: Evidence from FMCG Companies Listed In NSE

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ABSTRACT

A firm does not operate in vacuum rather there is an interaction between shareholders and stakeholders. Therefore, a company that has a board as part of its corporate governance is in a better position to improve management of its resources in addition to providing resources. This study aims to examine the relationship between Corporate Board Attributes and Working Capital Management of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) companies that are listed in National Stock Exchange (NSE) in India. Furthermore, it also investigates the impact of Corporate Board Attributes on Working Capital Management. This paper is purely based on secondary data. The data has been collected from the Annual Reports of 15 FMCG companies that are listed in NSE India over a 5-year period from 2020 to 2024. The data has been analyzed by using panel data regression model. The findings of the study suggest that board committee has significant positive impact on working capital management and board diversity as well board independence have negative but significant relationship with working capital management. However, there is no significant relationship between board size and board meetings. The study will help the policymakers, corporate managers, and investors to

understand the importance of corporate governance practices in financial management of FMCG companies.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of financial management is to maximize shareholders wealth. This requires a stable and adequate return for a company. Successful sales generate a stable return (Pandey, 2015), and in order to effect sales, the company must invest enough money in current assets known as working capital (WC). Boisjoly et al. (2020) state that "management of working capital is necessary to provide for the timing differences in the cash flow streams devoted to inventory, accounts payable, and accounts receivable." It enables firms to upgrade their liquidity positions and free up cash so they may plan long-term investments for growth and expansion (Dhole et al., 2019). Effective WC management boosts a firm's creditworthiness, profitability, and value (Prasad et al., 2019). The results of prior studies are complex and contradictory. According to one group of studies companies must invest a smaller amount in current assets, which would reduce the cash conversion cycle (CCC). Shorter CCC improves company performance by reducing investment in stocks and accounts receivable, lowering maintenance costs like storage and insurance, and freeing up funds for other uses (Ahangar and Shah, 2017). This fund can act as internal financing, which can be invested elsewhere. On the other hand, another group of studies suggests that higher investment in current assets results in longer CCC and firm's value. According to (Altaf and Shah, 2018) higher current assets, help continuous production, improve liquidity to pay for raw materials and expenses like wages and salaries, and help to lower the risk of refinancing and interest . However, an increased amount of current assets also includes costs like opportunity cost, bankruptcy cost and agency cost (Kieschnick et al., 2009; Ahangar and Shah, 2017; Altaf and Ahmad, 2019). On the other hand, low investment in current assets is also a threat to the production process and solvency position, which increases the cost of illiquidity (Altaf and Ahmad, 2019). The cost of opportunity, bankruptcy, and agency fees are also included in an increase in current assets (Kieschnick et al., 2009; Ahangar and Shah, 2017; Altaf and Ahmad, 2019). The above mentioned contradicting propositions necessitate the investigation of optimal WC for companies that improves performance. Even though it's important for companies to have optimal WC, companies in developing countries like India may not be able to keep it at that level due to a number of other frictions. Such frictions may be in the form of smaller and growing companies than developed countries, limited access to financial markets, more

dependency on institutional financing coupled with high-interest rates, higher political instability, poor corporate governance, uneven distribution of wealth, less developed financial market, etc. (Chauhan and Banerjee, 2018). Ahangar and Shah (2017) suggest that though investment in WC involves costs and benefits, such costs and benefits vary across the companies, leading to different levels of optimal WC. Consequently, some businesses may adopt an aggressive WCM policy, whereas others may adopt a conservative WCM policy. According to Pandey (2015), the WCM policy can be defined as the risk-return trade-off that the company uses to determine the ratio of its current assets to its fixed assets. This is due to the fact that both higher and lower levels of WC bring risk and return to the firm which results in various forms of cost and benefit. A conservative WC policy maintains higher levels of current asset than fixed assets to assume the risk of capital blocked in current assets and to leverage the benefit of uninterrupted production, short-term solvency, and sales growth through credit facilities. While aggressive WC policy aims to maintain lower levels of current assets in relation to fixed assets in order to maximize the use of available funds for productive purposes, reducing opportunity costs also reduces the costs associated with insurance, inventory holdings, credit sales etc. Therefore, finance executives must decide the appropriate WCM policy as deemed fit for the company.

However, to achieve these objectives, firms need to have systematic frameworks in place, with efficient monitoring devices and policies. This systematic framework is known as corporate governance, which is designed to ensure the transparency and accountability of those who are part of the firm's policy implementation group, so as to achieve better firm performance. Corporate governance is the system by which companies are directed and controlled. Boards of directors are responsible for the governance of their companies. The responsibilities of the board include setting the company's strategic aims, providing the leadership to put them into effect, supervising the management of the business and reporting to shareholders on their stewardship. Corporate governance is therefore about what the board of a company does and how it sets the values of the company, and it is to be distinguished from the day to day operational management of the company by full-time executives.

Consequently, size of corporate boards, independence of boards, frequency of board meetings, and dual role of CEO play a key role in business and might result in high cash balances, more amounts of receivables, high volume of trade payables, and a quick cash conversion cycle. Policies to manage Working Capital which are inefficient, prompted by weak corporate governance, have unfavorable influence on corporate owners' wealth. Working Capital policy adopted by a firm in which firms are maintaining high balance of working capital accounts depict risk averse behavior of management, which

may give rise to agency issues, as directors and the CEO might keep balances at that level, which may not maximize the wealth of owners of a corporation (Gill & Shah, 2012). Thus, a strong corporate governance mechanism can serve as a check on the handling firms' resources. An organization, that is not managing working capital efficiently, prompted by weak or poor corporate governance, will be in need of more resources to manage every day activities of the organization in comparison with peer organizations of the same level and hence may face adverse financial problems. Moreover, because of cash crisis, an organization may sacrifice future investment opportunities that can create value and might be unable to recompense their investors satisfactorily. Hence, it can be stated that an efficient governance mechanism of an organization might lead to efficient management of its working capital, which ultimately stimulate businesses to produce better financial results.

Working Capital Management (WCM) plays a critical role in ensuring a firm's operational efficiency, liquidity, and profitability. Effective WCM involves managing current assets and liabilities to optimize cash flow, particularly in capital-intensive sectors like the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) industry. Given the FMCG sector's reliance on fast inventory turnover, efficient management of the cash conversion cycle (CCC) and related components—Accounts Receivable Period (ARP), Inventory Conversion Period (ICP), and Accounts Payable Period (APP)—is essential for sustaining competitive advantage and improving financial performance.

Corporate governance, particularly the attributes of a company's board of directors, significantly influences managerial decisions, including WCM practices. Board characteristics such as size, independence, gender diversity, and board meeting frequency shape oversight mechanisms and managerial efficiency. For instance, independent directors may provide unbiased monitoring, while diverse boards bring varied perspectives that enhance decision-making.

Despite the growing importance of corporate governance in emerging economies like India, limited research exists on its impact on WCM, particularly in the FMCG sector. This study aims to bridge this gap by analyzing the relationship between board attributes and WCM among FMCG companies listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE). The findings will provide valuable insights for managers, policymakers, and investors on how corporate governance practices can drive efficient working capital management.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- **Naz et al., (2022)** made a research on “Corporate governance, working capital management, and firm performance: Some new insights from agency theory” of 179 non-financial firms listed in Pakistan Stock exchange from 2009-2018 and found that a corporate governance quality index and efficiency of working capital management are positively related to firm performance. Additionally, the results indicate that working capital management partially mediates the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance.
- **Al Faryan et al., (2022)**, examined the effects of corporate governance on the effectiveness of working capital management among 82 Indian pharmaceutical companies for ten years from 2008 to 2017. The results of the study revealed the number of directors on a board of directors negatively and significantly affects payables deferral period and receivables collection period, while composition of the board does not have a significant impact on the efficiency of working capital management.
- **Franzoi, (2021)** made a research on the impact of family board involvement on working capital management by taking into account 278 listed firms of Germany from 2000–2013. The results of the study showed that primarily the share of family members in the executive board increases the length of the cash conversion cycle (CCC), particularly in smaller and non-service firms. Most notably, family management increases the inventory period. The higher average equity ratio of family firms suggests that family firms may face reduced financing pressure to address such inefficiencies in current assets and current liabilities management. Furthermore, family-managed firms may be less professional in their working capital management.
- **Coleman et al., (2020)** examined the effect of corporate governance on working capital policy; Aggressive and Conservative of 103 firms listed on Nigeria and Ghana Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2016. Data extracted from the annual financial report. The result showed that corporate governance on implemented aggressive/conservative working capital policy by firms produced a mixed result. Aggressive working capital policy implementation calls for strict control mechanism to ensure less investment in current assets. Therefore, there is strong corporate governance influence on working capital management of firms that operate aggressive working policy than firms which have implemented conservative working capital policy.

- **Prasad et al., (2019)** explored the impact of corporate governance on the working capital management of Indian firms. The investigation was performed using balanced panel data procedures for a sample of 323 Indian non-financial firms listed in the Bombay Stock Exchange for the period 2007–2017. Findings of their study indicated that the CEO duality, one of the nine board indicators played a role in improving the working capital management of the sample firms. The default tax payment of the legal indicator and the additional information disclosure of the proactive indicators also had an effect on the working capital management of the Indian non-financial firms.
- **Narwal and Jindal (2017)** made a study on corporate governance and cash holdings of 96 firms of India and found that Director's Remuneration, Board size and number of Audit Committee Members are positively associated with cash holding whereas Non-Executive Directors and Board meeting are negatively associated with the cash holding.
- **Njoku (2017)** showed that work-capital management was closely connected with the board and audit committee, while durability of CEO and duality of CEOs were not linked to working-capital management.
- **Zadeh (2016)** attempted to study the Impact of Corporate Governance on Cash Management Efficiency in the Industry of Machinery and Equipment of Iran and proved that the corporate governance components (board size, CEO tenure and outside directors) were a significantly and positively associated with cash conversion cycle.
- **Goyal, Bansal, and Sharma (2015)** analysis showed that an expansion in board and audit committee autonomy contributed to taking a balanced approach to short-term capital management, which had a negative impact on the quality of working capital. The study also showed that power of a company weakened with the rise in board size.
- **Gill et al (2015)** examined the Impact of Independent Directors on the Cash Conversion Cycle of 189 American Manufacturing Firms and concluded that presence of independent directors in the board of directors helps in shorting the inventory period and cash conversion cycle which helps in shareholders wealth maximization.
- **Ifaradonbeh et al (2015)** studied the Impact of Corporate Governance on the Current Assets Management of 70 Companies Listed in Tehran Stock Exchange stated that good corporate governance of companies helped in improving the current ratio.

- **Achchuthan and Kajanathan (2013)** found out the significant difference between corporate governance practices on working capital management efficiency in listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. The results revealed that there is no significant mean different between the levels of working capital management efficiency among corporate governance practices as board committees, board meetings and proportion of non- executive director except board leadership structure.
- **A. S. Gill and Biger (2013)** revealed that the duality of CEO and the internationalization of the company have shown that they improve the ability to control receivables and payables accounts, improving the company's internationalization inventory and cash conversion cycle management capabilities. The tenure of CEO, the size and the financial performance of a company in the management of cash, and the ability to improve the current ratio and CEO duality and improve the financial performance of the direct impact in cash conversation performance.
- **Amarjit et al. (2013)** found that corporate governance improves the efficiency of working capital management of American manufacturing firms. Larger board size may not be in favor of American manufacturing firms because it does not improve working capital management efficiency. The results of the study generally support the tradeoff theory of cash holdings.
- **Kamau and Basweti (2013)** studied on the impact of corporate governance on working capital management of 42 Manufacturing Firms of Nairobi and revealed that Board size and CEO tenure were positively associated with working capital management but insignificant level and board meeting was negatively associated with the working capital management.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- a. To study the relationship between Corporate Governance Attributes and Working Capital Management.
- b. To investigate the impact of Corporate Governance Attributes on Working Capital Management.

4. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of Board Size on working capital management.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of Board Committee on working capital management.

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of Board Meetings on working capital management.

H₀₄: There is no significant impact of Gender Diversity on working capital management.

H₀₅: There is no significant impact of Board Independence on working capital management.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Data and Sample:

Population: FMCG Companies listed on NSE India

Sample: Panel data of 15 FMCG Companies from 2020-2024

Data Source: Secondary Sources (Annual Report, Research Papers published both online and offline)

5.2 Variables:

Dependent Variable: Working Capital Management (Cash Conversion Cycle)

Independent Variable: Corporate Board Attributes (Board Size, Board Committee, Board Meetings, Board Diversity and Board Independence)

Control Variable: Firm Size and Firm Age

5.3 Model Specification:

The panel Regression Model is as follows:

$$WCM (CCC) = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BC_{it} + \beta_3 BM_{it} + \beta_4 BD_{it} + \beta_5 BI_{it} + \beta_5 FS_{it} + \beta_5 FA_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where,

WCM= Working Capital Management

CCC= Cash Conversion Cycle

α = Constant

β = Coefficients

BS= Board Size

BC= Board Committee

BM= Board Meetings

BD= Board Diversity

BI= Board Independence

FS= Firm Size

FA= Firm Age

5.4 Estimation Techniques:

Descriptive statistics

Test of multicollinearity

Pooled Regression Model

6. RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Summary Statistics:

The Table-1 depicts the summary statistics of variables which illustrates the characteristics of the FMCG firms in the study offering a better understanding of their governance structures, financial dynamics and operational efficiency. The mean of CCC is -0.74, indicating that firms are collecting receivables and selling inventories faster than they are paying their creditors which is an indication of strong financial efficiency. Whereas, high standard deviation (41.96) indicates significant variability, with some firms having much longer or negative cycle might be due to the inefficiency in managing working capital. The average Board Size (BS) of around 11 strikes a balance between small and larger board.

Table-1: Summary Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	Min.	Max.
CCC	-0.74	1.11	41.96	-100.58	41.00
BS	10.65	10.00	3.14	6.00	19.00
BC	6.55	6.00	1.87	4.00	10.00
BM	5.93	6.00	1.63	4.00	14.00
BD	1.89	1.00	1.34	1.00	5.00
BI	5.85	6.00	1.71	3.00	10.00
FS	8.75	8.89	1.37	5.32	11.38
FA	3.03	3.04	0.26	2.30	3.40

Source: Authors' Calculation

The range of 6 to 19 reflects the lowest and highest number of directors in the board of most firms. Board Committee (BC) has a mean of 6.55 with the maximum of 10 and minimum of 10. This implies that moderate proportion of independent directors in the most firms and the lower SD indicates that most companies have same proportion of independent directors. Board meets 6 times (Mean=5.93) annually. The SD of 1.63 depicts moderate variation in meeting frequency. It may be due to the fact that some firms may require more frequent meetings than other due to simple operations or different governance practices. The mean (1.89) and median (1) value of Board Diversity (BD) suggests that most boards have very few women independent directors. The SD of 1.34 indicates a significant variation, meaning some boards have one or more women directors, but overall, women's representation on board is very low. In regards to Board Independence (BI), the uppermost numbers of independent directors in the board are 10 while some firms have lowest number of 3. The mean of 5.85 and median of 6 indicates

that the boards maintain a reasonable level of independence. The SD (1.71) shows that most firms have high number of independent directors while some firms may have fewer.

6.3 Test of Regression Assumptions

Before applying the multiple regression, it is necessary to check whether there is any strong relationship between independent variables or not. If it found so, then it leads to multicollinearity problem. Hence, through the calculation of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), we have tested the multicollinearity as shown in Table-2. From the table, it is evident that all VIFs are less than the threshold limit of 10. Hence, there is no multicollinearity.

Table-2: Test of Multicollinearity

Variable	VIF
FS	2.134
FA	2.606
BS	7.349
BC	1.373
BM	1.626
BD	1.461
BI	8.756

Source: Authors' Calculation

6.3 Relationship between Corporate Board Attributes and Working Capital Management

OLS Regression Model has been used to test the hypotheses and to study the impact of corporate board attributes on working capital management of FMCG companies listed in NSE India. The model demonstrates a moderate explanatory power with an R-squared of 0.481 and Adjusted R-squared of 0.391 which indicates that approximately 48.1% of the variation in CCC is due to the independent variables i.e. corporate board attributes. The OLS Regression model is statistically significant as p-value (F) is 7.02e-06

Table-3: Pooled OLS Results

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Const	112.76	0.02 **
FS	9.29	0.03 **
FA	-42.4552	0.08 *
BS	3.21	0.33
BC	9.69	0.00 ***
BM	-0.132926	0.96
BD	-6.04950	0.08 *
BI	-83.6995	0.02 **
dt_2	-15.3909	0.21
dt_3	-13.8468	0.26
dt_4	-9.13776	0.46
dt_5	1.99	0.87
R-squared		0.481
Adjusted R-squared		0.391
P-value (F)		7.02e-06

Notes: *, ** and *** indicate significant at 10, 5 and 1% levels of significance respectively.

Source: Authors' Calculation

The study has controlled for two variables i.e. firm size and firm age with the assumptions that large firms which have been listed for several years have improved working capital management as a result of better decisions taken by board of directors. Out of the two variables, firm size has a positive ($\beta=9.29$) and significant ($p\text{-value}=0.03<0.05$) relationship with CCC. This implies that larger firms take the advantage of economies of scale in managing working capital. There is a negative ($\beta= - 42.46$) impact of firm age on CCC as p-value is 0.08 which is less than 0.10. It states that older firms may face challenges like rigidity, inefficiency, slower adaptability etc leading to inefficient management of working capital. Variables like Board Size ($p\text{-value}=0.33>0.05$) and Board Meetings ($p\text{-value}=0.96>0.05$) are not statistically significant. It means that increasing the size of the board and frequency of board meetings do not affect cash conversion cycle (CCC). Hence, the null hypotheses H_{01} and H_{03} are accepted. There is a positive and significant relationship between Board Committee and working capital management (CCC) as indicated by $\beta=9.69$ and $p\text{-value}=0.00<0.05$. This states that change in the number of board members in the committee by 1 unit leads to increase in cash conversion cycle by 9.69 units. Hence, the null hypotheses H_{02} is rejected and concluded that there is significant relationship between board

committee and working capital management (CCC). There is also a negative ($\beta = -6.05$) and weak significant relationship between Board Diversity (BD) and working capital management as $p\text{-value} = 0.08$ which is less than 0.10. the presence of female directors on the board slightly decreases the working capital might be due to resistance to change, integration challenges, over emphasis on gender over competency etc. however, basing on the result, the null hypotheses H_{04} is rejected. It means there is significant relationship between board diversity and working capital management. A strong negative ($\beta = -83.70$) but significant ($p\text{-value} = 0.02 < 0.05$) relationship is observed between Board Independence (BI) and Working Capital Management (CCC). It implies that change in the number of independent directors in the board by 1 unit decreases the working capital by 83.70 units. Basing on this result, the null hypotheses H_{05} is rejected and concluded that the board independence has significant effect on working capital management.

7. CONCLUSION

From the findings it is found that board committee and board independence play a significant role in influencing cash conversion cycle which is a key indicator of working capital management. Specifically in case of larger and more independent boards tend to lead more efficient working capital management. However, board independence shows a strong negative relationship with cash conversion cycle which indicates that increased dependence on board may reduce the efficiency of working capital management. Whereas, variables like board size and board meetings do not have any significant effect on working capital management. It implies that increasing the size of the board or frequency of board meetings may not be enough to improve the working capital management efficiency. Presence of female directors on the board shows a weak negative impact on working capital management. The study concluded that large firms benefit from economies of scale positively affects the working capital management. Whereas the older firms due to factors like rigidity, inefficiency and slower adaptability cannot have effective working capital utilization. Therefore, corporate governance attributes, particularly the board committee and board independence are critical for the improvement of working capital management in FMCG companies.

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